

ACTUAL PROBLEMS OF INTERNAL DISEASES (THERAPY)

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Prevalence

Corona-virus disease 2019 (COVID-19) first occurred in Wuhan, China, in December 2019. As of April 15, 2020, more than 1.9 million COVID-19 cases had been confirmed worldwide, with over 120,000 deaths. To more effectively prevent COVID-19 proliferation, there is a pressing need to monitor and guess COVID-19 incidence. Time series models help anticipate the impact of the COVID-19 epidemic and determine how to respond to this catastrophe.

Purpose of Study

The clinical trials were conducted to find an effective treatment for covid19 pneumonia and new ways to improve health and decrease motility rate. Research study purposes to demeanor an appropriate calculation of the properties of the COVID-19 pandemic on the COVID-19 pneumonia.

Research materials or methods

COVID-19 patients were hospitalized at the period of Tocilizumab & remdesivir availability with 7-day hospital stay and ICU death rate. The research covered in this study looked at the same variables.

Results

112 patients were evaluated (82 were male, and 30 were female). These patients were matched using propensity scores to 21 patients who got standard of care (a combination of hydroxychloroquine, azithromycin and a prophylactic dose of low weight heparin). Remdesivir & Tocilizumab had no side effects. The study indicated that Tocilizumab had no effect on ICU admission day mortality compared to SOC. Laboratory tests revealed significant time-treatment associations for C-Reactive Protein (CRP), alanine aminotransferase (ALT), platelets, and international normalized ratio (INR). Regardless of treatment, lymphocyte count fluctuated over time.

How some of the Covid-19 vaccines compare

Company	Type	Doses	How effective*	Storage	Cost per dose
	62-90%	Regular fridge temperature	£3 (\$4)		
	95%	-20C up to 6 months	£25 (\$33)		
	95%	-70C	£15 (\$20)		
	92%	Regular fridge temperature (in dry form)	£7.50 (\$10)		

Conclusion

The COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in death and probable long-term damage in survivors following the initial infection. Antiviral medicines are rapidly evolving. To present, only Tocilizumab & remdesivir has been shown in clinical trials to reduce symptom duration but not mortality in COVID-19 patients hospitalized. Vaccine shows preventive role but first, there were observational studies with inconsistent results. Due to

the unpredictability of data, clinical trials are required to assess the medications' safety and efficacy. Most of the medicines we discussed were for sick individuals in hospitals. Non-hospitalized patients with the minor illness have no therapeutic choice. Like influenza treatments, we anticipate an antiviral treatment that may be safely given outpatient to stop disease progression and limit SARS-CoV-2 transmission.